

HISTORICAL SOCIETIES AND DIGITAL PRESERVATION CHALLENGES

BACKGROUND

Grid Heritage collects historic equipment, film footage, photographs and documents relating to electricity transmission in New Zealand.

THE CHALLENGE

How will historical societies like Grid Heritage pivot from physical to digital preservation?

CONCLUSION

By proactively preparing to receive digital records, Grid Heritage can safeguard the rich history of New Zealand's electricity transmission for future generations.

KEY QUESTIONS

How can small historical societies prepare themselves for receiving digital content and preserving digital formats?

What resources are available for them?

How does an amateur historical society obtain the necessary expertise that is required to properly preserve its historical records?

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